

EFFECT OF ELECTROLYTES ON THE STABILITY AND ELECTROKINETIC POTENTIAL OF VANADIUM PENTOXIDE AND CHROMIUM HYDROXIDE SOLS

BY B. N. GHOSH, R. N. ROY CHOWDHURY AND D. P. BURMAN

It has been observed that for the same rate of setting the electrokinetic potential of vanadium pentoxide sol in presence of different electrolytes is almost the same, the values ranging from -43 to -45 millivolts when the setting takes place in 2 minutes and from -35 to -37 millivolts when the setting takes place in 1 minute, the electrolytes used being chlorides of sodium, potassium, magnesium, barium, calcium and aluminium. The electrokinetic potential of positively charged chromium hydroxide sol has also been measured in presence of ferrocyanide, oxalate, sulphate, hydroxide and benzoate of potassium and for the same rate of coagulation with different counter ions, its value ranges from 24 to 25 millivolts. The results thus point to the existence of a critical zone of potential for the coagulation of these two sols.

Although the importance of electrokinetic potential in determining the stability of colloidal solutions has been fully recognised, yet there is much controversy over the existence of a critical potential at or below which the coagulation of a colloid by electrolytes can occur. In this connection reference should be made to the works of Powis (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1915, 89, 110; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 734), Kruyt and Willigan (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 130, 159), Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2963), Mukherjee and Ganguly (this *Journal*, 1930, 7, 465) and Mukherjee and Chowdhury (*Sci. & Culture*, 1935, 1, 111). In view of the conflicting results obtained by the different workers, much further work on this subject is necessary before a satisfactory conclusion can be drawn. The present investigation was undertaken with this object in view and the data obtained using vanadium pentoxide and chromium hydroxide sols are recorded in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Vanadium Pentoxide Sol.—The V_2O_5 sol was prepared according to the method of Blitz (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 1098) by treating a known weight of ammonium vanadate with slight excess of hydrochloric acid and washing the precipitate with distilled water until peptisation started. The precipitate was then shaken vigorously with the desired quantity of distilled water and subjected to dialysis. The dialysis was stopped when the water outside gave only a very faint test of chloride. The solution was stored in a stoppered Jena glass bottle and allowed to age for about a month.

Chromium Hydroxide Sol.—The positively charged chromium hydroxide sol was prepared by treating a concentrated chromic chloride solution with ammonium carbonate solution just insufficient to cause any visible precipitation and then subjecting the mixture to hot dialysis according to the method of Needle and Barman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 1961). When the chloride content of the outside solution was reduced almost to *nil*, the dialysis was stopped and the solution was transferred to a Jena glass bottle. The bottle was kept well stoppered.

206417 1958

206417 1958

Coagulation of Colloids by Electrolytes

(i) *Vanadium Pentoxide Sol.*—It has been observed that V_2O_5 sol sets to a gel on the addition of an electrolyte and this gel structure remains unbroken even on inverting the test tube. The time of gel formation varies with the concentration of the electrolyte added and is found to be quite sensitive to small changes in concentration of the electrolyte. The concentration of the various electrolytes, which bring about the setting of the sol in a definite time, say 2 minutes, is determined carefully. For this purpose 2 c.c. of the sol are taken in each of a number of test tubes and 2 c.c. of an electrolyte having different concentrations are added to each one of them from another set of test tubes. In each case, after addition of the electrolyte, the mixture is transferred back into the test tube from which the electrolyte has been added. Each tube is tilted now and then to see whether the colloid has set to a gel. Time required for setting is noted by means of a stop-watch. The concentrations of the electrolytes are so adjusted that the setting of the sol to gel takes place just in 2 minutes in one set of experiments and just in 1 minute in another set of experiments. The results are recorded in Table I.

(ii) *Chromium Hydroxide Sol.*—In the case of chromic hydroxide sol the concentrations of the different electrolytes which bring about its coagulation in a given time is determined in the following way.

The sol (2 c.c.) is taken in a test tube and 2 c.c. of an electrolyte of known concentration are added to it. The mixture after shaking is transferred to a centrifuge tube and centrifuged always at a definite speed for 5 minutes. After this the centrifuge tube is examined to ascertain if the particles have settled at the bottom occupying a definite volume and leaving the supernatant liquid clear. The concentrations of the various electrolytes, which just produce this desired effect, are taken to be equicoagulating. By the procedure described above the values of the equicoagulating concentrations of electrolytes are found to be reproducible within 5%.

Measurement of Electrokinetic Potential

The electrokinetic potential was measured by using an apparatus similar to that used by Mukherjee and co-workers (*Nature*, 1922, 110, 732) and also by Ghosh and Roy (this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 634). The electrokinetic potential has been calculated from the following equation derived by Perrin (*J. chim. phys.*, 1904, 2, 601).

$$\xi = \frac{4\pi\eta kv}{Di}$$

where ξ represents the electrokinetic potential; η , the coefficient of viscosity and D , the dielectric constant of the dispersion medium; v , the volume of the liquid flowing through the diaphragm per second and i , the electric current.

Formation of the Diaphragm

The solution (30 c.c.) was taken in a dry beaker and 30 c.c. of the electrolyte added to it with constant stirring so that the mixing was thoroughly done. A definite

volume of the mixture was then transferred to the U-tube of the electro-osmotic apparatus. The U-tube was put in a bag and centrifuged for 15 minutes always at a constant speed so that the degree of packing of the coagulum at the bottom of the tube was nearly the same in all cases. The remaining portion of the mixture was also centrifuged to separate the coagulum. The clear solution at the top in the case of chromium hydroxide sol was taken and its conductivity measured. In the case of vanadium pentoxide sol the specific conductivity of the mixture of the colloid and the electrolyte was measured. Next the U-tube and the side tubes were filled up with this clear liquid or a solution of an electrolyte of the same sp. conductivity. The electrokinetic potential of the coagulum was determined by the electro-endosmotic method as already described, and the results are recorded in Tables I and II. It should be noted here that with vanadium pentoxide solution the different electrolytes used as coagulator (e.g., NaCl, KCl, CaCl₂, BaCl₂, MgCl₂, and AlCl₃) have the same anion, only the cations, which are directly responsible for the coagulation of the negatively charged solution differ. The electrolytes were selected in this manner to eliminate any irregularity which might have caused by different anions. Further, in order to study the effect of valency on coagulation cations of different valency (uni, bi and tri) have been used. With chromium hydroxide solution, the cation has been kept the same, while the nature of the anions has been varied to study their effect on the coagulation of the solution.

TABLE I

Electrokinetic potential of V₂O₅ sol in presence of different electrolytes.

Dielectric constant (*D*) = 81.

Conc. of the electrolytes.	Time of coagulation.	Sp. conductivity (κ).	Electroendosmotic flow in c.c. per sec.	Current (δ).	Electrokinetic potential.
Sodium chloride solution.					
0.0750 <i>N</i>	2 min.	0.00770 mho	0.0006992	0.02 amp.	-43.6 m. volts
0.0825	1	.01140	.0003804	"	-35.1
0.0925	0	.01143	.0004030	"	-26.6
0.1000	0	.01200	.0003272	"	-22.7
Potassium chloride solution.					
0.024	2	0.00343	0.001154	0.015	-42.8
0.0230	1	.00400	.001103	0.020	-35.8
0.0237	0	.00400	.001033	"	-31.8
0.0300	0	.00500	.000488	"	-19.8
0.0448	0	.00750	.0003876	"	-16.8
Barium chloride solution.					
0.0015	2	0.0004800	0.004330	0.0075	-45.0
0.0016	1	.0005300	.003720	.0090	-35.2
0.0018	0	.0005583	.002689	"	-25.7
0.0030	0	.0007500	.001556	.0100	-13.5
0.0060	0	.0012000	.000568	"	+ 9.5

TABLE I (contd.)

Conc. of the electrolytes.	Time of coagulation.	Sp. conductivity (κ).	Electroosmotic flow in c.c. per sec.	Current (i).	Electrokinetic potential.
Calcium chloride solution.					
0.00136 N	2 mins.	0.0005106 mho.	0.004065	0.0075 amp.	-44.8 m. volts.
0.00148	1	.0004890	.003543	.0080	-35.4
0.00200	0	.0005854	.002670	.0080	-22.0
0.00273	0	.0007273	.001677	.0090	-15.9
Magnesium chloride solution					
0.00165	2	0.0005106	0.005348	0.010	-44.2
0.00186	1	.0004800	.003832	.008	-37.2
0.0033	0	.0007384	.001912	.008	-20.5
0.0045	0	.0008889	.001744	.010	-17.9
Aluminium chloride solution.					
0.000813	2	0.0002960	0.006298	0.007	-43.1
0.00085	1	.0004800	.002714	.006	-35.2
0.001625	0	.0005217	.000775	.006	-7.8
0.0025	0	.0006048	.000439	.006	-0.8

TABLE II

Electrokinetic potential of chromium hydroxide sol in presence of diff. electrolytes.

Dielectric constant (D) of medium = 81.

Conc. of the electrolyte.	Sp. conductivity (κ).	Electroosmotic flow in c.c. per sec.	Current (i).	Electrokinetic potential.
Potassium benzoate.				
0.03125 N*	0.003871 mho.	0.000775	0.0215 amp.	23.1 m. volts
Potassium hydroxide.				
0.0135*	0.002034	0.001320	0.0215	20.4
0.0150	.002162	.000388	"	6.5
0.0165	.002297	- .000388	"	- 6.9
0.0180	.002400	- .001215	"	-22.4
Potassium sulphate.				
0.0110*	0.001880	0.001718	0.0215	25.6
0.0120	.002180	.001307	"	21.5
0.0132	.002243	.000956	"	16.5
0.0150	.002504	.000584	"	11.8
0.0180	.003000	.000388	"	8.9
0.0200	.003240	.000258	"	6.4
0.0250	.003934	.000103	"	3.1

TABLE II (contd.)

Conc. of the electrolyte.	Sp. conductivity (κ).	Electroosmotic flow in c.c. per sec.	Current (i).	Electrokinetic potential.
Potassium oxalate.				
0.011 [*] N	0.001928 mho.	0.001550	0.0215 amp.	23.0 volts.
0.012	.002000	.001068	"	16.4
0.0132	.002180	.000400	"	6.7
0.015	.002500	-.000174	"	- 3.4
0.050	.006960	-.000347	"	-20.7
Potassium ferrocyanide.				
0.00275 [*]	0.001811	0.0001666	0.0215	23.2
0.00285	.001975	.001330	"	20.2
0.00315	.002133	.000258	"	4.2
0.00350	.002254	-.000905	"	-15.7
0.00400	.002487	-.001253	"	-24.0

^{*} Indicates equicoagulating concentrations.

DISCUSSION

It will be noted from the data recorded in Table I that the concentrations of the electrolytes required to bring about the transition from the sol to the gel state in the case of vanadium pentoxide solution, follow in general the Linder-Picten-Schulze-Hardy valency rule. The trivalent aluminium ion is more effective than the divalent ions and the latter, more effective than the monovalent ions. Of the two monovalent ions, sodium and potassium, the latter is decidedly stronger than the former in producing gel formation.

The data recorded in the same table show that as the concentration of an electrolyte increases, the magnitude of the electrokinetic potential of vanadium pentoxide gel diminishes.

If we compare electrokinetic potential of the gel at those concentrations of the different electrolytes at which the setting of the sol takes place in 2 minutes, we find that the value is fairly constant, lying between -43 and -45 millivolts. Furthermore, at those concentrations at which setting takes place in one minute, the electrokinetic potential of the gel ranges between -35 and -37 millivolts. If the rate of setting is taken as a measure of the degree of instability of the vanadium pentoxide sol then the results recorded above are in agreement with the theory of critical potential.

The coagulation of chromium hydroxide sol has been measured using such electrolytes as potassium benzoate, potassium hydroxide, potassium sulphate, potassium oxalate and potassium ferrocyanide. In this case also the valency rule for the coagulation of the colloids has been found to hold good. If the concentrations of the different electro-

lytes required to bring about the coagulation of the sol in 5 minutes be compared among themselves, it will be noticed that their coagulating power is in the following order

Ferrocyanide > oxalate > sulphate > hydroxide > benzoate.

It will also be noticed from the data recorded in Table II that the electrokinetic potential of chromium hydroxide sol diminishes almost linearly with the increase in concentration of the electrolytes. In some cases the electrokinetic potential has actually been reversed in sign with the use of higher concentrations of the electrolytes. If the electrokinetic potential of the colloidal particles in presence of equicoagulating concentrations of the different electrolytes be compared it will be noticed that its value ranges between 21 and 25 millivolts.

The results so far obtained with chromium hydroxide and vanadium pentoxide sols therefore indicate that these sols become unstable when their electrokinetic potential on an average falls below 23 millivolts and 44 millivolts respectively. These observations therefore support the 'theory of critical potential' regarding the coagulation of colloids.

DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA.

Received March 24, 1950.